

FAUNAL RECORDING METHODS

Bagno Grande | San Casciano dei Bagni

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Zooarchaeological recording methodology and data organisation

This document details recording methods for faunal material from Bagno Grande at San Casciano dei Bagni (Siena) excavated between 2021–2024 and published in: Trentacoste, A. (2025 – in press) Animals in and beyond the sanctuary: preliminary zooarchaeological results. In E. Mariotti, A. Salvi and J. Tabolli (eds), *Il Santuario Ritrovato 3. Oltre il Bronzo. Rapporto Preliminare di Scavo al Bagno Grande di San Casciano dei Bagni* (2023-2024). Livorno: Sillabe

Recording methodology

Element representation

All specimens which could be identified were recorded, and the presence of diagnostic zones was noted. Diagnostic zones were based on those of Bertini Vacca (2012) and are depicted in figures 1–3 below. In order to be counted, more than 50% of the specific zone needed to be present. Diagnostic zones were defined as:

- Teeth: occlusal surface (zone 1)
- Cranium: zygomaticus (zone 1), supraorbital margin (zone 2), occipital condyle (zone 3)
- Horncores/antlers: circumference at horncore base / antler burr (zone 1)
- Scapula: articulation (zone 1) and neck (zone 2)
- Pelvis: ischial (zone 1), ilial (zone 2), and pubic (zone 3) parts of the acetabulum
- Humerus: medial side of proximal articulation, head of humerus (zone 1); lateral tuberosity (zone 2); proximal diaphysis (zone 3); distal diaphysis (zone 4); lateral part of distal articulation (zone 5); medial part of distal articulation (zone 6)
- Femur: medial side of proximal articulation, head of femur (zone 1); lateral tuberosity (zone 2); proximal diaphysis (zone 3); distal diaphysis (zone 4); lateral part of distal articulation (zone 5); medial part of distal articulation (zone 6)
- Radius: medial side of proximal articulation (zone 1); lateral side of the proximal articulation (zone 2); proximal diaphysis (zone 3); distal diaphysis (zone 4); lateral part of distal articulation (zone 5); medial part of distal articulation (zone 6)
- Ulna: proximal head of *processus olecrani* (zone 1); articulation (*incisura semilunaris* and *processus coronoideus lateralis*) (zone 2); body/shaft (zone 3)
- Tibia: medial side of proximal articulation (zone 1); lateral side of the proximal articulation (zone 2); proximal diaphysis (zone 3); distal diaphysis (zone 4); lateral part of distal articulation (zone 5); medial part of distal articulation (zone 6)
- Metapodials – *Cattle, caprines, cervids, equids*: medial side of proximal articulation (zone 1); lateral side of the proximal articulation (zone 2); proximal diaphysis (zone 3); distal diaphysis (zone 4); lateral part of distal articulation / condyle (zone 5); medial part of distal articulation / condyle (zone 6)
- Metapodials – *Pigs, dogs, rodents*: proximal articulation (zone 1); diaphysis (zone 2); distal articulation (zone 3).
- Astragalus: lateral half (zone 1); medial half (zone 2).
- Calcaneum: *tuber calcanei* (zone 1); body/substantaculum (zone 2), distal point/articular surface (zone 3)
- Third carpal and scaphoid: more than half of complete element present (zone 1)
- Phalanges I and II: proximal articulation (zone 1); distal articulation (zone 2)
- Phalanx III: articulation (zone 1)
- Atlas: left half (zone 1); right half (zone 2)
- Axis: anterior half (zone 1); posterior half (zone 2)

Diagnostic zones on shells were represented by the apex in gastropods and umbo in bivalves.

Long bone and cranial fragments, ribs, and vertebrae were attributed to size classes (large, medium, small mammal) and counted. Indeterminate fragments were counted.

Preservation, modification, taxon determination

The preservation of the bone surface was recorded on an ordinal scale from 1 (very poor) to 5 (very good). Butchery modifications were recorded as chop, cut, or saw marks, with their location and an interpretation of their purpose noted. The presence of burning and gnawing was also recorded.

Taxa with similar morphology were distinguished with reference to published guidelines for sheep/goat (Zeder and Lapham 2010, Zeder and Pilaar 2010), red deer/fallow deer (Lister 1996), rabbit/hare (Callou 1997), and small mammals (Chaline 1974). Pigs were recorded without distinction between wild and domestic type, with observations recorded if the specimen appeared large enough to represent wild boar. Faunal remains were identified in the field laboratory at San Casciano and using reference collections at The British School at Rome and Museo delle Civiltà (Rome).

Measurements

Measurements were taken following von den Driesch (1976), Payne and Bull (1988), and Davis (1992):

- Molars and dP₄: L; bovids: W; suids: WA, WP; canids: M1 L and W (von den Driesch #13)
- Mandibular molar rows, canids only: P1–M3L (#8), P2–M3L (#9), P1–P4L (#11), P2–P4L (#12), M1–M3L (#10), H(#19)
- Pelvis: LA, LAR
- Femur: GL, Dc, SD
- Humerus: GL, Bd, BT, HTC, SD
- Radius: GL, Bp, Dp, Bd, Dd, BFp, BFd, SD
- Tibia: Bd, Dd, SD
- Astragalus: GLI, GLm, Bd, DI,
- Calcaneum: GL, GB
- Metapodials: Bd, BatF, SD, Bp, Dp; a, b, 1, 2, 4, 5 from Davis (1992) - bovids only; Dd, Bp, Dp - equids only.
- Cattle first phalanx: GLpe, Bp, SD, Bd

Age at death

Tooth wear stages were based on Payne (1973, 1987) for sheep/goats, and Grant (1982) for cattle and pigs. Sheep/goat mandibles assigned to age groups based on Payne (1973); pig and cattle mandibles were classified following O'Connor (1988).

For analysis of bone fusion, specimens were grouped into early, middle, and late fusion groups following Silver (1969) for cattle and equids, Zeder (2006) for sheep/goats, and Zeder, Lemoine et al. (2015) for pigs. These groupings correspond with early, middle, and late fusion groups defined as: cattle <18 months, 24–42 months, 42–48 months; sheep/goats <12 months, 12–30 months, 30–48+ months; pigs <18 months, 18–48 months, 48–60 months; equids <20 months (early), 36+ months (late).

Data structure

Specimens were recorded in MS Access and exported to a single CSV file with the following structure:

General information

ID	Specimen identification number. For teeth and jaws the ID number is preceded by a 'T'.
Site	San Casciano dei Bagni – Bagno Grande
US	Stratigraphic unit / context number
Area	Excavation area
Year	Year of excavation
Period	Chronological period
ContextNotes	Notes on contexts of particular interest

Taxon, element, and bone fusion

Element.Code	Code for skeletal element
Element	Skeletal element
Side	Left/Right
Taxon.Code	Code for taxon
Taxon.Latin	Taxon binomial name
Taxon.Eng	Taxon English name
Taxon.Group	Taxon group for zooarchaeological analysis
Z1	Presence (P) of diagnostic zone 1
Z2	Presence (P) of diagnostic zone 2
Z3	Presence (P) of diagnostic zone 3
Z4	Presence (P) of diagnostic zone 4
Z5	Presence (P) of diagnostic zone 5
Z6	Presence (P) of diagnostic zone 6
Count.Frag.Diaphysis	Count of long bone diaphysis fragments
Count.Frag.Epiphysis	Count of long bone epiphysis fragments
Count.Other	Count of other fragments

Total.Sp	Total number of specimens represented in the row in the CSV table
Fusion.Prox	Proximal fusion - fused (F), fusing (G), unfused diaphysis (UD), unfused epiphysis (UE), joining unfused diaphysis and epiphysis (UX)
Fusion.Distal	Distal fusion - fused (F), fusing (G), unfused diaphysis (UD), unfused epiphysis (UE), joining unfused diaphysis and epiphysis (UX)
<i>Preservation and modifications</i>	
Bone.Preservation	Surface preservation of specimen on ordinal 1–5 scale (5 = excellent)
M_1_type	Type of butchery mark present. T = cut. P = chop. S = saw. W = worked bone object.
M_1_func	Interpretation of butchery mark function: P = split/break open the bone. D = carcass dismemberment/separation of bone from another bone. F = filleting. S = skinning. W = bone working and associated debris. VV = for vertebrae: divided in half.
M_1_zone	Location of the butchery mark on the bone. Number indicates zone where mark was observed (see figures 1–3 below). A slash '/' is used to indicate when marks occur on the border of zones, e.g. 3/4 = mark observed at the border between zones 3 and 4.
M_2_type	Recorded if a second butchery mark is observed. Same as above.
M_2_func	Recorded if a second butchery mark is observed. Same as above.
M_2_zone	Recorded if a second butchery mark is observed. Same as above.
Burning	Evidence of burning. S = singed (small area of bone burnt). B = burnt (majority of bone burnt). C = majority of the bones is calcined.
Gnawing	Presence of gnawing marks. C = carnivore. R = rodents. H = herbivore.
<i>Further observations and details</i>	
PathNotes	Notes related to pathologies
AgeNotes	Notes related to age
SizeTypeNotes	Notes related to size, mostly used in relation to horse/donkey and pig/wild boar
Joins	Joining elements/animal bone groups. Indicated by a letter assigned to each group
Comments	Other comments
<i>Measurements</i>	
GL	Measurement - von den Driesch. GLpe for 1st phalanges. GLI for astagalus.
GLP	Measurement - von den Driesch
BG	Measurement - von den Driesch
LG	Measurement - von den Driesch
Bp	Measurement - von den Driesch
BFp	Measurement - von den Driesch
Dp	Measurement - von den Driesch
BT	Measurement - von den Driesch
Bd	Measurement - von den Driesch
DI	Measurement - von den Driesch
Dd	Measurement - von den Driesch
Dc	Measurement - von den Driesch
HTC	Measurement - Payne and Bull
LAR	Measurement - von den Driesch
SLC	Measurement - von den Driesch
SD	Measurement - von den Driesch
Lm	Measurement - von den Driesch
BatF	Measurement - von den Driesch
MP_a	Metapodial condyle measurement - Davis
MP_b	Metapodial condyle measurement - Davis
MP_1	Metapodial condyle measurement - Davis
MP_2	Metapodial condyle measurement - Davis
MP_3	Metapodial condyle measurement - Davis
MP_4	Metapodial condyle measurement - Davis

MP_5	Metapodial condyle measurement - Davis
MP_6	Metapodial condyle measurement - Davis
GB	Measurement - von den Driesch
Comments	Other observations, comments, and notes
Sampled	Details on sampling for further study (e.g. bioarchaeological)
<i>Teeth</i>	
Loose.or.Jaw	For teeth and jaw fragments - loose tooth (L) or jaw (J). A jaw is defined as a tooth having adjacent to it at least another half tooth/alveolus or an equivalent length of bone. A row of 2+ adjacent/joining teeth from a single individual is recorded as 'jaw' even if no bone is present.
ZTeeth	Presence (P) of diagnostic zone on any teeth
I1	Presence (P) or absence
I2	Presence (P) or absence
I3	Presence (P) or absence
I	Presence (P) or absence
dI1	Presence (P) or absence
dI2	Presence (P) or absence
dI3	Presence (P) or absence
dI.dC	Presence (P) or absence
C	Presence (P) of canine. In pigs the sex is recorded as male (M) or female (F) where possible. (See below for pig alveoli.)
dC	Presence (P) or absence
P1	Presence (P) or absence
P2	Presence (P) or absence
P3	Presence (P) or absence
P4	Presence (P) or absence
P	Undetermined premolar. Presence (P) or absence.
dP2	Presence (P) or absence
dP3	Presence (P) or absence
dP4	Wear stage or presence (P)
dP4L	Max length
dP4WP	Max width bovids, posterior width pigs
M1	Wear stage or presence (P)
M1L	Max length
M1WA	Max width bovids, anterior width pigs
M1WP	Posterior width
M1hyp	Presence (P) of hypoplasia
M2	Wear stage or presence (P)
M2L	Max length
M2WA	Max width bovids, anterior width pigs
M2WP	Posterior width
M2hyp	Presence (P) of hypoplasia
M3	Wear stage or presence (P)
M3L	Max length
M3WA	Max width bovids, anterior width pigs
M3WC	Width of central pillar (pigs)
M3hyp	Presence (P) of hypoplasia
M12	Wear stage or presence (P) - undetermined first/second molar
M12L	Max length

M12WA	Max width bovids, anterior width pigs
M12WP	Posterior width
M12hyp	Presence (P) of hypoplasia
M	Undetermined molar. Presence (P) or absence.
P.or.M	Undetermined premolar/molar. Presence (P) or absence.
P1.to.M3.L	Measurement - von den Driesch 8
P2.to.M3.L	Measurement - von den Driesch 9
P1.to.P4.L	Measurement - von den Driesch 11
P2.to.P4.L	Measurement - von den Driesch 12
M1.to.M3.L	Measurement - von den Driesch 10
Alveolus	Empty pig alveolus: male (M) or female (F)

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Figure 1 Diagnostic zones on the cranium, mandible, scapula and pelvis

Figure 2 Diagnostic zones on the humerus, radius, femur and tibia

Figure 3 Diagnostic zones on metapodials, astragalus, calcaneum, phalanges, atlas and axis

